

COMPARISON OF TEACHERS ATTITUDE IN KOSOVO AND IN TURKEY REGARDING EDUCATION

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Abstract:

The aim of this study is to compare teacher's attitude in Kosovo and in Turkey regarding education. With this aim, attitude survey was administered to teachers in Turkey and in Kosovo. In addition to the descriptive statistics, the results of the survey were analyzed by independent samples t-test. At the end of the study, it was found that attitudes of Kosovo's teachers were high in comparison to teachers in Turkey.

Keywords: mathematics education, attitude, attitudes toward mathematics, mathematics teaching

1. Introduction

At the end of the previous half century with the rapid changes in the world's process of globalization, and especially in the current quarter important developments in information, communication and technology have led to enormous changes in social, political and economic issues. These changes developed physical, geographic and disciplinary boundaries and it caused to the formation of new structures. This change has probably been the most experienced in the higher education area. However; the importance of knowledge increases fast in the world, the consequent "*information*" concept and understanding of "*science*" are changing, technology advances, concepts of democracy and governance are going to be different, and all the skills of the individuals who expect society to adapt to these changes are also changing. As in every field, the field of education must change because the education is the most important tool for development of the country in every aspect and individuals to live in dignity.

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In the historical period, societies gave place to different applications related to education. Teachers have the most critical role in the education system. Countries give a special importance to teacher training to organize their education system. While looking at the teacher training process it seems to be different practices in different countries. The theoretical information given in the Faculty of Education as well as making the application appears to be in the foreground [1]. Multicultural education involves educational policies and practices that meet the individual educational needs of population groups belonging to different cultural traditions. The intercultural education, minority or majority education policies provide a creative way to teach the majority of the people who interact with each other and belong to different cultures and practices. Accepting intercultural education, recognizing differences and diversity with tolerance, it is emphasized in particular that the objective protects the identity of each group [2].

Kosovo has become the world's newest country by declaring its independence on February 17th, 2008. Its young population, geostrategic location, and underground riches, has the potential to make strides in a short time in the economy. If taken in sufficient foreign investment, such a breakthrough will be easier. This country has the highest unemployment rate in Balkans, so educational activities are carried out in parallel with the difficulty already. The reason is that the physical infrastructure in the education sector and training equipment failure is not at the desired level. Contributions to training activities that will shape the future of the country are seen as a highly significant contribution to children and young people. The future of this country maintains with, well-trained, knowledgeable, a creation of a sustainable generation who are the owner of the enlightenment. Therefore, the people of the country need to receive a good education system its rightful place in the community and well-trained teachers are needed. In the future financial and spiritually satisfied teachers, will be established by their found the interest and reputation in the eyes of society and the state in wait will surely be bright [3].

Up to now, teacher's training has been one of the very important and difficult tasks. It appears that in overall, teacher training system has very little differences in all branches, which resemble each other. In Kosovo, teacher education system has been revised, particularly in the postwar era. In this context, starting with the 1990 independence movement in Kosovo has been created a sense of understanding of education policy and teacher training. Based on this approach June 6, 1997, in Pristina University Senate, it was decided to establish the Faculty of Education. According to this project, the aim of faculty is to train the teachers, both theoretically and practically in a quality manner, lessons and other educational activities envisaged in the plans and programs to support them to perform successfully [1].

The purpose of Kosovo Pristina University Faculty of Education is to use new methods and techniques, which can choose that the methods and techniques are best suited for which course and implemented, changes and developments followed, and to train questioning teachers [4]. For many years, there was only a state university in Kosovo until 2010 within the boundaries of different states. The number of universities with the establishment of the University of Prizren in 2010 has increased to two. However, as a result of the OECD's Thematic Survey of the National Policy on Education in Kosovo, completed in 2001, the teacher's teacher training program in Kosovo is not seen as a given specialty. Teacher training in Kosovo is based on rather academic and focuses, mainly on issues related to education which is at a high level. Teaching experience and reflective teaching methods are carried out without any systematic viewpoint or set specific goals and objectives [5]. In short, to increase the capacity of higher education and dissemination in Kosovo the distance was taken, but in recent years has not come to the desired level yet. Quantitatively this rapid change is accepted as a very positive development, but this development is to what extent in a parallel qualitative change is not exactly clear. On the one hand, increasing access to higher education institutions of higher education brought about an increase in the enrollment rate and equal opportunities, that needs to reveal more about quality. Therefore, this research, on teachers who work in Kosovo, is planned to investigate the attitudes towards the teaching profession.

As a result of rapid changes in our daily lives, teaching forms of educational institutions is changing in parallel. Instead of educating memory-oriented individuals, there is a need to educate individuals who are using knowledge, thinking, researching, questioning, and solving problems, mental, emotional and social aspects. Traditional understanding grows individuals are unable to adapt to scientific and technological developments and they can't contribute to the country's development as it required. Therefore, how to question and examine the training of individuals in the future, which approaches, methods and techniques to use is important. Because the training, provides to individuals to understand the physical world and it helps to the social interactions of a wide range of knowledge and skills in hardware [6].

In Turkey, even education and training in this field are associated with different attitudes and perceptions on many issues, there are notable teachers in the education system. That because the teacher's professional equipment directly affects the quality of the teaching and learning the process. Therefore, to perform the role of the education system successfully cultivating and employment of qualified teachers in the system there is a need for serious responsibility to raise the education in success. The individual's behavior in the educational process is expected to be a change. The purpose of the individual through education, information, behavior, attitudes are changing. The

individual is who in the education process; is supposed to be in the positive direction of these changes [7]. Students attitude towards mathematics, have been investigated from various angles and at many different levels. For example, students' mathematics and attitudes towards mathematics emerged about their feelings is very important in mathematics education [8]. In this context, some research [9, 10] examined gender differences in attitudes toward mathematics, mathematics anxiety in some research, attitudes towards mathematics and mathematics education [11, 12] has been studied.

Especially teacher's attitude belief and the behavior towards primary school mathematics that creates positive student's attitude and behavior toward mathematics is considered by researchers to be a significant factor [13]. In math students succeed or fail and the role of attitude in mathematics, love cannot be denied. Attitudes are the psychological structures located in the emotional nature of the behavior, which cannot be observed directly.

Attitudes and success influence each other [14, 15]. Attitude is not acquired from birth, but it is acquired after birth [16]. Özlü in his research attitude, "*...is a result of the individual's past experience and experience that occurs pre-formed opinion and it is not an observable behavior, it is a trend preparatory action*" [17]. Tavşancıl searcher, "*...is the result of life and experiences about having a dynamic router or power to influence the individual's behavior with regard to all objects and situations is the emotional and mental readiness*" [18]. In contrast, Katz, argues that "*depending on the system of values that an individual has a symbol, an object, a person or the world, good or bad, useful or a pre-thinking that detect the harmful aspects*" [19]. Maqsud specifically attitudes towards mathematics is defined as "*...individuals like or dislike math, dealing with mathematical activity or escaping from the tendency of it, the belief of the success or failure and it's a cumulative measure whether mathematics is beneficial or not*" [20].

2. Literature Review

Baloğlu study on Psychological and emotional character of the individuals are examined for personal reasons. Attitudes towards mathematics are one of the most studied personal reasons in mathematical anxiety. It is stated that there is the negative relationship between mathematics anxiety and the attitudes towards mathematics [21].

Bütüncü in his research study Developing Attitudes are time-consuming, it is resistant to change after growing trend and is difficult to develop. The change of attitude is very difficult to change and it takes the time to change newly formed attitude. There are many external factors, leading to attitude formation. The stimuli around the individual may change the attitudes of interaction with individuals or individuals can acquire new attitudes [22].

Bodur in his article found formation and change of attitudes in interpersonal relations have also gained much experience through the contribution of an individual's life [23]. In Gökdere aim of this study contributes to the implementation by determining and solving the problems encountered in the inclusive practices by developing an assessment instrument comparing the attitude, concern and interaction levels of pre-service and in-service elementary teachers towards inclusive education. The final results of this study suggest that professional development workshops and seminars on special and inclusive education would improve the knowledge of in-service elementary teachers and enhance the qualification of the inclusive practices [24].

MacFarlane and others study examined teacher beliefs and behaviors with respect to children with SEBD. Teachers who attended more INSET sessions were more positive. But more experienced teachers were less willing to work with this group [25]. Ohle and others in their study examining teachers' attitudes towards diagnostics, motivation towards diagnostics, self-efficacy beliefs and self-reflection in diagnostics with regard to teaching with multi-representational learning material. In the study provides evidence of the structure and importance of teachers' attitudes, motivation, and self-related cognitions [26]. According to the studies, there is a positive correlation between success and attitude [27, 28, 29].

Ertem and Alkan researchers argue that learning retention and availability of individuals depend on the attitude they have developed for the subject or branch [30]. Therefore, teachers' attitudes towards the teaching profession are also important and this research will focus on the comparison between the attitude of the teachers in Kosovo and in Turkey.

For this purpose, it was found out to answer the following research problems:

1. *How is the teachers' attitude towards teaching profession in Turkey?*
2. *How is the teachers' attitude towards teaching profession in Kosovo?*
3. *Is there any significant difference between the teachers in Turkey and the teachers in Kosovo in terms of the attitude toward teaching profession?*

3. Procedure

In this chapter; Information on data collection conducted to determine the attitudes of the teaching profession and teachers who participated in the survey are included in quantitative analysis.

3.1 Research Model

In this research, there will be attempted to reveal an existing condition. Therefore, this research is performed by using a survey scan pattern. One of quantitative research methods in the screening model is described as a condition in the past or as a still existing model [31].

3.2 Study group

The research population constitutes by the teachers who work in schools in Kosovo and Turkey in the fall semester of 2015-2016 academic year. The research was not made in the sample of study and in the fall semester 2015-2016 academic year, probability-based sampling methods among the teachers who work in schools in Turkey and in Kosovo have been created a total of 187 teachers randomly determined by sampling. In a random sampling method, samples are selected completely randomly [32]. In this research, the importance was given to the teachers who participated in willingly. A number of teachers who are working in Kosovo is 92 (49.7%) and the number of teachers who are working in Turkey is 93 (50.3%).

3.3 Data Collection Tools, Data Collection and Analysis of Data

The data of this research is used to measure the attitudes towards the teaching profession Aşkar and Erdem (1987) developed the attitude scale which was applied and collected from the participants. Approximately the participants lost 10 minutes to complete this scale. Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient of scale teacher attitudes towards the profession is calculated as 0.8 and 5 points Likert-type scale was prepared. In the scale there are 10 items, 5 items are negative and 5 items are positive.

The data obtained from the answers to the items on the scale of respondents "*totally agree*" and "*disagree completely*" set between the ends was carried out by 5 degrees. Participants' responses to each of the 10 items of the scale were scored from 1 to 5. The highest and the lowest score that can be taken from this scale is between 50 and 10 points. At this stage, the participating students have been reached the average score as a result of dividing the total number of points obtained from the material substance of the scale. In order to interpret the scores, wide range of intra-group score designated as $(5-1) / 5 = 0.80$. As a result, the range of the answers that the participants gave to the scale are "totally agree 4:21 to 5:00, 3:41 to 4:20 agree, undecided 2.61-3.40, 1.81-2.60 disagree and 1.00-1.80 totally disagree".

In the analysis of the data, in addition to descriptive statistics, independent samples t-test was used.

4. Findings

As part of this research, "How are the teachers' attitudes towards the teaching profession in Turkey?"; when searching for the answer to the first research problem in the form of the average scores they receive from the scale of the research involved teachers from Turkey have been examined and the percentage and frequency values for these points are presented in Table 1 at below.

Table 1: Distribution of Attitudes toward Occupation
Rate of Participants in Turkey

Attitudes points									
1.00-1.80		1.81-2.60		2.61-3.40		3.41-4.20		4.21-5.00	
between points		between points		between points		between points		between points	
f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
0	0.0	2	2.2	17	18.3	52	55.9	22	23.7

In the analysis, more than half of the teachers who participated in the research from Turkey (55.9%) answered in the scale "agree" that received average scores from 3:41 to 4:20. However, the majority of teachers (79.6%) were found to have a positive attitude towards the teaching profession.

"How are the teachers' attitudes towards the teaching profession in Kosovo?" When searching for the answer to the first research problem, the average scale scores they receive from teachers were examined participating in Kosovo and relating to these points frequency and percentage values are presented in Table 2 located below.

Table 2: Distribution of Scores of Participants Attitude towards
Teaching Profession in Kosovo

Attitudes points									
1.00-1.80		1.81-2.60		2.61-3.40		3.41-4.20		4.21-5.00	
between points		between points		between points		between points		between points	
f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
3	3.3	0	0.0	2	2.2	21	22.8	66	71.7

In the analysis, the scale of a significant proportion of teachers who participated in the research from Kosovo (71.7%) corresponds to answer "strongly agree" that they received average scores from 4.20 to 5.00. However, the teachers surveyed in Turkey received scores of 22.8% corresponding to the same answer. In this case, the teachers who are working in Turkey have lower attitudes of the teaching profession compare to the

teacher who is working in Kosovo. Therefore, in order to examine the differences between Kosovo and teacher candidates' attitudes towards the teaching profession in Turkey, independent samples t-test was used.

Table 3: In relation to the variation of the attitude scores of participants independent sample t-test results

Teachers	N	$\bar{x}$	S	sd	t	p
Kosovo	92	4.43	0.74	183	5.63	0.00
Turkey	93	3.89	0.57			

*p>.05

As seen from the table above, participants' attitudes towards the teaching profession between Turkey and Kosovo is verified that there is a significant difference ($t_{183}=5.63$, $p>.05$).

The participants examined in relation to attitude scores, an average of the attitudes points towards teaching profession of teachers participating in Kosovo ($\bar{x}=4.43$) was found high comparison to teachers in Turkey.

5. Conclusion and Suggestions

In this study, the attitudes of teachers in the teaching profession in Turkey and Kosovo were examined. As a result, of the examination of attitudes towards the teaching profession from teachers who participated in the research, it was found to be high in Kosovo's teacher's comparison to teachers in Turkey. Establishing a link between math lessons with everyday life it is thought to increase success in mathematics. In addition, the researchers can investigate the factors that affect the success of Kosovo and Turkish teachers, and also there is a need to increase the teachers achievement academically. The importance of teachers' attitudes toward mathematics learning process requires effective measure. Developing a positive attitude toward mathematics is going to gain importance. Although, the change of attitude in mathematics requires a long time it is not impossible.

Various studies have focused on the impact on the attitudes of different applications outside and inside the classroom [33, 34, 35, 36] in order to develop positive attitude towards mathematics special teaching methods, classroom management and personal development of students research will make a great contribution to mathematics education.

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